

FISHERIES IN UZBEKISTAN AND MODERN METHODS IN THE FIELD

Hakberdieva Hilola Abdusaid qizi

Gulistan State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7752235>

Abstract. *This article contains a number of scientific observations on the topic of fisheries management in Uzbekistan and modern methods in this area. We hope that it will be useful to many.*

Keywords: *fisheries, human health, fishing net, investment projects, vitamin, quality.*

To organize fisheries in our country, it is necessary first of all to determine its type and economic structure. The composition of the farm and the capacity of production are also given. All construction works are carried out on the basis of approved projects. It is important to choose a place for this. Such activities are carried out on the basis of the land legislation of each country. In this regard, the total area of land will be different.

In particular, it can be 300-1000 ha for full-system farms, 25-50 ha for hatcheries and 20 ha or more for fish ponds. Fish farming is the fattening of fish in ponds and other bodies of water. Breeding and development of fish in pond farming is of great importance. It is carried out on the basis of a special system.

Pools are always provided with water. A method of feeding zhogora, khanbalik, perch, pike and other fish has been developed. Ponds for keeping heat-loving fish are built in swampy and swampy areas, and water is taken from streams, canals, collectors and ash. Cold-loving fish ponds are built in areas with a low content of organic matter. they get their water from springs and streams. A special fence is placed at the inlet and outlet of water from the pond to prevent foreign fish from entering the cage. A fish pond will be built on the bank of a small river, with the expectation that it will be used for other purposes in the future. To maintain the fish pond in good condition for a long time, measures are taken to improve its reclamation condition. These activities are held outside the pool and in the pool. The first includes dividing the slope of the catchment area into steps, cleaning the water that enters the pond and enriching it with oxygen, blocking flood waters, and preventing pond turbidity. periodic drying of the pond, creating the necessary water-air regime, preventing the growth of weeds such as reeds, dew, preventing the formation of peat layers in the pond, cleaning the bottom of the pond from silt and other debris are the activities of the second group.

For feeding fish, barley, wheat and rye bran, fish meal, meat meal, etc. are used. Fish food is served on a special table (the table is immersed in water by 0.5-0.75 m) or placed on a special feeding area arranged at the bottom of the pond. The water temperature is taken into account when feeding the fish. Fish feed well on corn feed at a water temperature of 20-26 °, khanbalik - 15-18. The ameliorative state of the pond is improved by breeding fish, each of the ponds is designed to perform a specific task. For example, fish fry is grown in spawning grounds. Fish larvae are fed twice a day, in the morning and in the evening. After 10 days, these fish were released into large ponds, and after a month their weight reached 0.25 g.

These ponds are dug wider to warm the water faster and easier. Plants grow under them. Because without plants, carp will not spawn. After that, the fish are transferred to ponds, where

their juveniles are grown. With the advent of winter, these small carp fish migrate to deep waters. They are called winterers. With the advent of spring, one-year-old carps are released into large pools. In these ponds, daphnia and cyclops are bred as natural food. In this pond, carp are fed corn, sorghum, baked potatoes and bone meal. With the advent of autumn, grown carps are caught.

Cultivation of carp fish in rice fields in the regions of our republic is considered an important factor in achieving high efficiency. For example, they swim all the time and soften the soil, eating mosquito larvae and fungi, as well as weeds and seeds in the water, while performing the important task of getting a good harvest from rice. Thus, fishery work in rice farming is yielding results. Other species of fish also feed in the lake. He is growing fast. Adapted to eating all kinds of food, loves warm water. Good results are obtained at a water temperature of 18-20°C for spawning and 20-28°C for rapid growth. If the water temperature drops to 13-14°C, it stops feeding and flows without movement. In general, their growth and development depend primarily on water temperature, availability of nutrients in the water, and proper storage.

Carp weighs 500 g at one year of age, 1000 g at two years of age and 3000 g at a young age. They reach sexual maturity at the age of 4-5 years. Females produce an average of 180,000 eggs (caviar) per kg of body weight. Carp belongs to the group of fish that prefer warmth. They are biologically identical to carp. In gray conditions, carp grow a little slower than carp. But some representatives during life can weigh up to 20 kg. Lakka is a fish belonging to the lakka family. Height up to 5 m, weight about 300 kg. The body is thin, the flippers are small, the mouth is wide, the lower jaw is longer. Mustache 3 pairs. The back is olive and the underside is white. Lakka fish lives in lakes, rivers and other places of the Aral Sea and Europe. In June it publishes 136-467 thousand wars. Sexually mature at the age of four years. Currently, this is 7% of the annual fish catch of the Aral Sea. It feeds on invertebrates and vertebrates. White carp, white and gray carp.

They belong to the carp family. They are more common in rivers flowing into the Pacific Ocean, in the rivers of Asia and in the southern part of the Amur . Okay, carp mostly feed on soft water plants. The white mullet feeds on phytoplankton and algae.

Figure 1. Pond fish

Feeds on phytoplankton and zooplankton . In the south of Central Asia, female white-tailed deer reach sexual maturity at the age of 3 years with a body length of 40 cm. Grass carp and grass carp reach sexual maturity at the age of 3-4 years, when the body length reaches 60 cm. They lay eggs only in running water. If there is no running water, eggs will not be laid. Spawning requires a water temperature of 19-20°C. Depending on their size, the number of eggs ranges from 100-200 thousand to 1 million, sometimes even more. White carp often weighs 300 g of stone. Their weight is 1000 eggs per kg. They feed on aquatic plants and therefore benefit greatly by cleaning the canals that supply water to cotton and rice fields. Salmon is a family of fish belonging to the herring family. The body is densely covered with scales. It lives in freshwater reservoirs of the Northern Hemisphere.

REFERENCES

1. Tikhomov. Basics of fishing. Textbook. Tashkent. "Vostok", 2001.
2. Abdurakhmanov T.A. "The spread of parasitic diseases in fish". Journal of Agriculture of Uzbekistan 2003.
3. Abdurakhmanov T.A., Khakberdiev P.S. "Diseases of fish". Text of lectures. Samarkand 2003
4. Allamuratova G.B. Parasites of fish in the Khorezm basin and ways to combat them. The abstract of the dissertation was written for the degree of Candidate of Biological Sciences. Tashkent, 2011, 22b.
5. Akhmedov Kh.Yu., Shoyokubov R.Sh. Methodological guide to improve the productivity of ponds by stocking grass carp in ponds. XF "Carrlo" Tashkent 2006
6. Ziyonet.uz
7. wikipedia.uz
8. www.lex.uz